

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTION IN HEALTH CARE SERVICES BASED ON PATIENT SATISFACTION- REVIEW ON LITERATURE AND ITS APPLICATIONS

Suphala Kotian, Vijaya Parameshwari,** Rashmi M****

Key words: patient satisfaction, health care service, quality indicator for patient satisfaction.

Abstract:

Health care standards that are influenced by the patient satisfaction is clinical outcomes and patient retention. Hence understanding the depth of patient satisfaction is a burning issue in the present trend which witness high competition in health care organisations. although various attempts were made to measure patient satisfaction, neither of the studies prove conclusive. Hence to explore the challenges in measuring the patient satisfaction, and providing the solution for quality health care services, the present article is written.

Objective: To explore evidence on the relationship between patient satisfaction and patient care services, its challenges and solution.

Design: systematic review

Research site: literature pertaining to the studies done in Primary and secondary care which includes hospitals and health care centres.

Result: The present study analyses evidence from 23 studies, out of which 11 studies were analysed based on the objectives of the present study. It was found that there is consistent positive association between the patient satisfaction and clinical effectiveness. There is also positive association between effective communication.

Conclusion: the literature when reviewed and analysed in the present study show the patient satisfaction is influenced by various factors like patient experience, clinical effectiveness. The article also highlights that the effective communication regarding the health care process should not be sidelined. Hence all these dimensions should be considered for patient satisfaction.

Introduction

Prime indicator used from ages since, to measure the quality in health care is Patient satisfaction. Patient satisfaction level provides a benchmark for clinical outcome and patient retention which is a health care standard for the professionals.

Hence health care professionals find patient satisfaction as a very effective indicator to determine their success. This factor is essential in the present era, which witnesses the establishment of several specialty hospital and competition is extremely high. Due to development of social media, print media, web media and various other sources, awareness among the customers awareness regarding health care facility is at its peak. Customers of health services are also supported by the third party like insurance companies, Government programs and other collaborations who play a leading role in creating awareness. Investors and participants in health care are also aware about the lawsuits for any complexity while availing services.

The health care services are provided to the people in need through the professionals. The patients here become the consumer and buyer of health services in terms of treatment and quality services in the health care unit. In the area where service is given to the customer, involves a multidisciplinary team including medical professional, para medical staff, managerial staff, general staff, and housekeeping, Hence, the scope of quality health care service is very wide in any health care organisation. The expanse of quality service begins at the entrance of the customer to their discharge. Therefore, we can visualise the wide area in which the satisfaction of the patients to be studied in depth, in order to provide a quality care. A broad range of challenges are brought in view to understand the expectations of the patients. When we

* Professor Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka

** Professor & HOD, AJ Institute of Hospital Administration, under the affiliation of RGUHS Mangalore, Karnataka

*** Assistant Professor, Father Muller College of Allied Health Sciences, Kankanady, Mangalore, Karnataka

discuss about the challenges of patient care services, we need to include area of doctor patient relationship, patient satisfaction and the organisation policies and regulations. The medical professionals have a major responsibility of providing best health promoting decision and treatment. The health care organisation must be functional on providing compassion and care to the customers. Health care facility in the hospital

should be transparent by the general staff, who creates an effective communication atmosphere for efficient doctor patient interaction.

Based on this area the present article is planned, which will analyse various literatures pertaining to the satisfaction level of the patients in a health care facility, the challenges faced by the hospitals and the strategies to improve retention of the customers. Finally, it aims to bring quality care to the patients availing health care facility.

The article provides analysis of various literature based on areas pertaining to challenges of patient satisfaction in health care services, level of patient satisfaction in various areas, tools administered to measure patient satisfaction, and finally strategies to improve patient satisfaction. Finally the authors will discuss the areas to promote patient satisfaction and strategies to improve the standard in quality health services care.

Challenges of patient satisfaction in health care services:

Patient satisfaction is of prime importance in any health care organisation. Although various research is conducted by the experts, the result remains indecisive. It is a major challenge for the health care professionals because the evidence for the determinants of patient satisfaction is still not found.

Author Enkhjargal Batbaatar et.al¹ in one of their systematic review of literature, reported that there is need for robust measurement system for patient satisfaction. It is required as per the authors because, the determinants of patient satisfaction are still inconclusive. The major challenge is that there is a contradicting evidence across the patient satisfaction studies. The study conducted using a systematic review in areas of PubMed, CINAHL and Scopus in 2014, which included 109 articles. The authors reported that the review of these literature was not able

to indicate the specific potential characteristics which influence the most in patient satisfaction. There was wide variation in the sociodemographic characteristics. Hence, the authors concluded that assessment of patient

satisfaction should focus on cultural, behavioural, and socio-demographic differences that will affect the patient satisfaction using a standardised questionnaire.

Patient satisfaction in various areas

Needs, expectation of the customer varies from time to time. With the definition of WHO (1948), health is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing not merely the absence of disease or infirmity². This clearly explains the goal of health care. But the present trend of health care simply explains the history-examination-investigation-treatment and the outcome. The health care process is mechanically operated, whereas in reality the health care should include the minimisation of burden of the disease. This process would bring satisfaction among the patients.

Various areas in which the patient expectation of satisfaction may include The doctor patient interaction, duration of waiting time, comfortability in waiting area, reception of the patients, sign boards, medical record management, constancy in appointment time, investigation procedure, discharge time, follow up etc. Various studies were conducted to find the criteria for patient satisfaction where few of them were analysed by the authors.

Study conducted by Prakash B³ discuss that patient satisfaction is one of the important indicators to measure quality in health care, which is commonly used by many of the health professions. He discusses that patient satisfaction has an impact on clinical outcome, patient retention and medical malpractice claims. Although this patient satisfaction report is acts as a substitute, the health care professionals can consider it as an effective indicator. The article also discussed in view to the patient satisfaction in dermatological practice and esthetic practice.

We can anticipate another major challenge faced by the health care organisation that is to satisfy the patients is high expectations of the patient. The grievance generally lies on the less interaction of health care professionals with the patients. This viewpoint is consistent with the study conducted by Moigan Lotfi et.al.⁴ Result of the

study reviewed that there should be improvement with the communication professionally, and the health care professionals has to reconsider the priorities of the activities performed in the process of health care. Similar result is also found in another study conducted by Williams S et.al.⁵ states that increased patient satisfaction is perceived if the process follows patient centeredness and empathy during consultations. Here the authors have highlighted a challenge that is lack of measurement and control for other input factors like patient mood state, that may have an impact on satisfaction rates.

Interesting information was derived in the study conducted by Brahmania M et.al.⁶ who conducted a prospective study in outpatient gastroenterology clinic in Canada. The study compared a patient satisfaction when seen by a trainee and attending physician with an attending physician alone. The study was conducted in 11-month duration with 211 patients. The univariate analysis showed that the patient had good experience when seen by the attending physician alone rather than trainee and attending physician (73% versus 56%), however in multivariate analysis, no significant difference was found ($p=0.931$). however, the study also highlighted that physician factors was found to be associated with high patient satisfaction in addressing the patient concerns ($p=0.021$)

Tools to measure patient satisfaction

Measuring the level of patient satisfaction is rather incredibly challenging task. As in the literature of Williams S et.al.⁶ it was reviewed that there is extraneous variable functioning on the process of measurement, like the mood of patient, during of their hospitalisation etc. So various literature was reviewed on how to measure the level of patient satisfaction.

Cathal Doyle et.al.⁷ explored evidence on the links between patient experience and clinical safety and effectiveness outcomes. They conducted a systematic review which summarised evidence from 55 studies. It was reported that there is a consistence positive association between various factors like patient safety, and clinical effectiveness like settings, study design, disease area etc with the satisfaction level. The study highlighted that patient experience is very important and hence it is very important measure to study the quality in health care. Patient

experience in this study means self-rated and objectively measured health outcome, adherence to medication and treatment and preventive care like screening service and immunisation. Together with this few of the relational dimension like clinician ability to empathise, respect the preference of the patient, inclusion in decision making and providing information to enable self-care also need to be included. It also gave importance on the medical professional in being honest and transparent. Another dimension being functional aspect was based on attending physical needs of the patients, timeliness of care, clean and safe environment, effective coordination between the professionals, and continuity. Hence the study concluded that patient experience, clinical effectiveness and patient safety should be taken as a group for any measurement.

Janet HY Ng et.al.⁸ conducted a study to explore the attributes of the patient satisfaction in broader health care context. To explore in-depth, the authors used Rodgers method, an inductive analysis. The study explored few attributes like provider attitude, technical competence, accessibility, and efficacy. The study also concluded that perception of the patients of their expectations, patient demographics and personality and the market competition were considered as a prerequisites of patient satisfaction. The authors at the end reported that the consequences of patient satisfaction were patient compliance, clinical outcomes, loyalty, and referrals.

Social media is considered as one of the important measurements of patient satisfaction as reported by Simon Geletta⁹ in one of the studies. The author tried to evaluate the supplementing the patient satisfaction survey with social media measurements. The study derived the data from the consumer review social media site called 'Yelp'. This source is useful when any geographically identifiable representation of the measurement is required like the target relevant population, and it is a possible source for population-based formal satisfaction measurement for health care services. This was the only study to collect the data that is evaluated the use of 'Yelp' as per the authors report.

Another review of the study conducted by Quintana JM et.al.¹⁰ identified few of the socio-demographic variables like length of stay, influence of education during visiting and intimacy and the influence of marital status in comfort

and visiting which was correlated positively during multivariate analysis. Hence the author confirms that these areas should be included when studying the satisfaction level of the patients.

Strategies to enhance patient satisfaction

Patient satisfaction promotes standard in health care and after understanding the level of their satisfaction, it is the responsibility of the organisation to implement it. Literature brought varied views regarding the expectations of the patients, their changing needs, and hence tailor-made strategies should be framed for the growth of the health industry.

In one of the literatures reviewed, authors Mojgan Lotfi et.al.⁴ reported that patient's dissatisfaction was due to the ineffective communication between the health care professionals and patients. They conducted a study in Burn wards at the Sina Hospital of Tabriz in 2018. The aim of the study was to find whether the professional communication between nurse and patient has any significant role in patient satisfaction. The result reported that there was a significant correlation with nurse patient communication and the patient's satisfaction level especially with the sex variable. Hence the authors concluded that it was hospital managers priority to improve patient satisfaction level. The strategy they suggested was to educate the hospital staff, especially nurses, along with identifying motivating factors and dissatisfaction factors improved patient satisfaction.

In another study conducted by C Charles¹¹ reported that, there should be 'effective provider-patient communication' including the all the information to be given to the patients, providers respect for patients preferences, attending patients physical care needs, educating patients regarding their medication and tests, improving the quality of relationship between patient and physician in charge, educating and communicating the patients family regarding care, information about the pain management and hospital discharge planning. Their study also revealed that among the 4599 patients included as the study sample, 41% reported that they had not been told about the daily hospital routines. 20% of the patients said that they were not told about the medication side effects. 20% of them were not informed about the investigation reports. 36% were not informed about the pain management. During discharge, 39% of them reported that they were not

educated about the danger signs to observe at home, when to resume normal activities. This study highlights that effective communication should be compulsory adhered between the provider-& patient.

Conclusion and Discussion

Patient satisfaction survey aids in understanding the patients needs, expectations and limitations in the health care unit, which will help the researcher to improve the process of health care service. This will help the health care provider to maintain professional standards and develop the health care industry. The present article highlights the importance of patient satisfaction after availing the health care services.

Majority of the health care organisation use data collection method in the form of feedback to collect information of patient satisfaction. We see high level challenges in this method. Data collection is conducted as on-site survey, where data is collected directly from the patients who are experiencing the problems. This type of data collection initially will focus on the doctor-patient communication. So the author analyse that the satisfaction level of the patients revolves around three factors i.e firstly the Health care professionals like Doctors, para medical staff and administrative staff, including patient-doctor relationship, type of communication, time given to the patient, empathy etc, secondly patient which includes his demographic profile, needs, demands, expectations, and experience and thirdly the organisation which includes the environment, provisions, facilities and the staff communication. Hence the health care providers has to shoulder twin responsibility of providing best health care to the patient as well as leading the hospital team towards satisfying the patient. The health care organisation or the management has also the responsibility of building a service-oriented culture. This could be rendered by introducing certain standards based on the requirement of the patients. It may include various stages. It begins with the receiving of the patients till the discharge. There also should be hospital policy adhering to the standard protocol like the triage system. The

esthetics of the organisation, waiting time of the patients, medical record management, pharmacy facilities, investigation process, reporting procedures, and the patient education during investigation, treatment and payment process and finally the discharge procedures. As one of the studies that is reviewed indicates that the

time of deriving feedback also influences the level of satisfaction. Hence the hospital needs to promote effective communication to satisfy the grievance of the patients. The policies and procedures should be transparent to the patients and the attendant.

Patient feedback depends on the perception of the patients based on their expectation. Hence it could be considered only as a substitute of other indicators like retention of the patients, reference to public, successful outcome of the treatment etc. However, since the organisation need to measure quantitatively about the level of satisfaction, patient experience is of prime importance. Patient experience varies from individual to individual. Hence few factors like health outcome, adherence to medication and treatment and interest in preventive and followup behaviours should be included in measuring the patient satisfaction.

To conclude the authors of the present study, comprehend that tailor made strategies are required to promote patient satisfaction in any health care industry. Understanding the expectation of the patients during admission, their needs and demands should be understood at the first stage of the admission, thus allowing them to avail services as they desire. The policies and rules of the organisation should be made aware in the second stage. Importance also should be given to the doctor patient communication, where patient education should be a priority activity. A friendly hospital environment should be given importance where grievances of the patient and the attendants should be attended immediately. There also should be regular training programs to the health care providers in the organisation.

limitation of the present study: Although the present study approaches the systematic review by binding most of the literature published by various authors, it is found to be time limited review, hence the authors identify a wide scope to expand this review-based study on wider area to uncover further evidence.

Conflict of Interest statement: None.

REFERENCES:

1. Batbaatar E, Dorjdagva J, Luvsannyam A, Savino MM, Amenta P. Determinants of patient satisfaction: a systematic review. *Perspect Public Health*. 2017 Mar;137(2):89-101. doi: 10.1177/1757913916634136. Epub 2016 Jul 20. PMID: 27004489.
2. WHO Preamble to the Constitution of the World Health Organization as adopted by the International Health Conference, New York, 19-22 June, 1946; signed on 22 July 1946 by the representatives of 61 States (Official Records of the World Health Organization, no. 2, p. 100) and entered into force on 7 April 1948.
3. prakash, bhanu “. “Patient satisfaction”. *Journal of cutaneous and aesthetic surgery*. 2010;3(3): 151-5. doi:10.4103/0974-2077.74491
4. Lotfi M, Zamanzadeh V, Valizadeh L, Khajehgoodari M. Assessment of nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction from nursing care. *Nurs Open*. 2019 Jun 26;6(3):1189- 1196. doi: 10.1002/nop2.316. PMID: 31367445; PMCID: PMC6650658
5. Williams S, Weinman J, Dale J. Doctor-patient communication and patient satisfaction: a review. *Fam Pract*. 1998 Oct;15(5):480-92. doi: 10.1093/fampra/15.5.480. PMID: 9848436.
6. Monk SM, Nanagas MT, Fitch JL, Stolfi A, Pickoff AS. Comparison of resident and faculty patient satisfaction surveys in a pediatric ambulatory clinic. *Teach Learn Med*. 2006;18(4):343–7. doi: 10.1207/s15328015tlm1804_12.
7. Doyle C, Lennox L, Bell DA systematic review of evidence on the links between patient experience and clinical safety and effectiveness *BMJ Open* 2013;3:e001570. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2012-001570
8. Ng JHY, Luk BHK. Patient satisfaction: Concept analysis in the healthcare context. *Patient Educ Couns*. 2019 Apr;102(4):790-796. doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2018.11.013. Epub 2018 Nov 19. PMID: 30477906.
9. Geletta, S. (2018), “Measuring patient satisfaction with medical services using social media generated data”, *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*, Vol. 31 No. 2, pp. 96- 105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHCQA-12-2016-0183>
10. Quintana JM, González N, Bilbao A, Aizpuru F, Escobar A, Esteban C, San-Sebastián JA, de-la-Sierra E, Thompson A. Predictors of patient satisfaction with hospital health care. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2006 Aug 16;6:102. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-6-102. PMID: 16914046; PMCID: PMC1579213.

11. Charles C, Gauld M, Chambers L, O'Brien B, Haynes RB, Labelle R. How was your hospital stay? Patients' reports about their care in Canadian hospitals. *CMAJ*. 1994 Jun 1;150(11):1813-22. PMID: 8199958; PMCID: PMC1337056.
12. Thornton RD, Nurse N, Snavely L, Hackett-Zahler S, Frank K, DiTomasso RA. Influences on patient satisfaction in healthcare centers: a semi-quantitative study over 5 years. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2017 May 19;17(1):361. doi: 10.1186/s12913-017-2307-z. PMID: 28526039; PMCID: PMC5438500.
13. Mikael Rahmqvist, Ana-Claudia Bara, Patient characteristics and quality dimensions related to patient satisfaction, *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, Volume 22, Issue 2, April 2010, Pages 86–92, <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzq009>
14. Glickman, S., Boulding, W., Manary, M., Staelin, R., Roe, M., Wolosin, R., Ohman, E., Peterson, E. and Schulman, K., 2010. Patient Satisfaction and Its Relationship With Clinical Quality and Inpatient Mortality in Acute Myocardial Infarction. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Quality and Outcomes*, 3(2), pp.188-195.
15. Ali Anbori, Sirajoon Noor Ghani, Hematram Yadav, Aqil Mohammad Daher, Tin Tin Su, Patient satisfaction and loyalty to the private hospitals in Sana'a, Yemen, *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, Volume 22, Issue 4, August 2010, Pages 310–315, <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzq029>
16. Alfred M, Ubogaya K, Chen X, Wint D, Worrall PS. Effectiveness of culturally focused interventions in increasing the satisfaction of hospitalized Asian patients: a systematic review. *JBISIRIR- 2016-003048*. PMID: 27635753.
17. Tadele Melese et al. Assessment of client satisfaction in labor and delivery services at a maternity referral hospital in Ethiopia. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2014;17:76. [doi: 10.11604/pamj.2014.17.76.3189]
18. Al-Abri, R., & Al-Balushi, A. (2014). Patient satisfaction survey as a tool towards quality improvement. *Oman medical journal*, 29(1), 3–7. <https://doi.org/10.5001/omj.2014.02>
19. Gustke, S., Balch, D., West, V. and Rogers, L., 2000. Patient Satisfaction with Telemedicine. *Telemedicine Journal*, 6(1), pp.5-13.
20. Xesfingi S, Vozikis A. Patient satisfaction with the healthcare system: Assessing the impact of socio-economic and healthcare provision factors. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2016 Mar 15;16:94. doi: 10.1186/s12913-016-1327-4. PMID: 26979458; PMCID: PMC4793546.
21. Karaca A, Durna Z. Patient satisfaction with the quality of nursing care. *Nurs Open*. 2019 Jan 4;6(2):535-545. doi: 10.1002/nop2.237. PMID: 30918704; PMCID: PMC6419107.
22. Prakash, B., 2010. Patient satisfaction. *Journal of Cutaneous and Aesthetic Surgery*, 3(3), p.151.
23. Fenton JJ, Jerant AF, Bertakis KD, Franks P. The Cost of Satisfaction: A National Study of Patient Satisfaction, Health Care Utilization, Expenditures, and Mortality. *Arch Intern Med*. 2012;172(5):405–411. doi:10.1001/archinternmed.2011.1662